

A STUDY OF SOCIAL SKILLS OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

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Abstract

This study attempts to compare the social skills of the higher secondary school students in relation to their socio-economic status. The objectives of the study were to compare the social skills of government and non-government higher secondary school students in relation to their socio-economic status, to compare the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls in relation to their socio-economic status and to compare the social skills of higher secondary school students of rural and urban area in relation to their socio-economic status. Null hypotheses have been formulated in this study. The researcher has used descriptive method in this study. Stratified random sampling technique has been used to select 600 students from the government and non-government higher secondary schools of district Haridwar. Social skill is the dependent variable of the present study whereas socio-economic status is the independent variable of the present study. Mean, S.D. and two-way analysis of variance have been used for the statistical analysis. Findings revealed that a significant difference has been found in the social skills of government and non-government school students. Students of government higher secondary schools had better social skills as compared to the students of non-government higher secondary schools. There has been found a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status. Students of higher secondary schools who have high socio-economic status had highest level of social skills. No significant difference has been found in the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls. Significant difference has not been found in the social skills of higher secondary students of rural and urban area.

Keywords: Social Skills, Higher Secondary School Students and Socio-Economic Status.

INTRODUCTION

A child is born in a society and also grows up in the society. How a person behaves with others in the society depends on his social development. Social development depends on factors such as peer relations, good social adjustment with others, emotional intelligence, family structure, social skills, etc. (Namka, 2009). Social skills help in holding conversations with others, starting and maintaining relationships and friendships. Basically social skills are behaviors that promote positive interaction with others (Lynch & Simpson, 2010). According to Zins, Weissbert, Wang, & Walberg (2004), “social skills can also be defined within the context of social and emotional learning - recognizing and managing our emotions, developing caring and concern for others, establishing positive relationships, making responsible decisions, and handling challenging situations constructively and ethically”. Good social skills are very important for an individual for successful functioning in life, by learning these skills a person comes to know how to make good decisions, good choices and how to behave in diverse situations.

Social skills help to prepare young people to be mature and succeed in their adult roles with the family, workplace and community. Social skills help people in their academic, personal and future professional activities and to adjust in their social life. Social skills help people to succeed in their personal, academic, social and future professional activities (Elias, 1997). Basically, social skills are the components of behavior that help to adapt across the variety of social settings and enable to get adjusted in the society. Good social skills help us to know what to say to others, how to ask others for help, how to maintain good relationships in the society etc. Social skills help people to express their positive and negative feelings in interpersonal situations (Mafra, 2015).

Social skills play an important role in every situation whether it may be for the children in the age of their schooling or for the adults in their career. Social skills play a very important role in adolescents also. Adolescence is the period in which transition from childhood to adulthood takes place. Rapid physiological and psychological changes occur in the children in this stage. Now, children begin to mature and they extend their relationships beyond their family. They face identity crises in this age and are in the need to make their own identity. They need to have better social skills to develop good relationships and make their identity. Considering the importance of social skills, the researcher decided to examine the social skills of the students in relation to their socio-economic status.

Statement of the Problem

A Study of Social Skills of Higher Secondary School Students in relation to their Socio-Economic Status

Operational Definition of the Key Terms

1. **Social Skills :** In the present study, the scores obtained by students on ‘Social Skills Rating Scale’ developed by ‘Vishal Sood, Arti Anand and Suresh Kumar’ are considered as their social skills.
2. **Higher Secondary School Students:** In the present study, higher secondary school students are those students who are studying in class 12 in the different government and non-government higher secondary schools of district Haridwar.
3. **Socio-Economic Status:** In the present study, the scores obtained by students on ‘Socio-Economic Status Scale’ developed by ‘Sunil Kumar Upadhyay and Alka Saxena’ are considered as their socio-economic status.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the present study are as follows:

1. To compare the social skills of government and non-government higher secondary school students in relation to their socio-economic status.
2. To compare the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls in relation to their socio-economic status.

3. To compare the social skills of higher secondary school students of rural and urban area in relation to their socio-economic status.

Hypotheses of the Study

Following null hypotheses have been formed in the present study:

1. There is no significant difference in the social skills of government and non-government higher secondary school students in relation to their socio-economic status.
2. There is no significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls in relation to their socio-economic status.
3. There is no significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students of rural and urban area in relation to their socio-economic status.

METHODOLOGY

1. **Method of the Study:** The researcher has used descriptive method in this study.
2. **Sample and Sampling Technique:** In the present study, stratified random sampling technique has been used to select 600 students from the government and non-government higher secondary schools of district Haridwar. The sample comprised of 300 rural and 300 urban students.
3. **Variables:** Social skill is the dependent variable of the present study whereas socio-economic status is the independent variable of the present study.
4. **Research Scale Used:** Social Skills Rating Scale developed by Dr. Vishal Sood, Dr. Arti Anand and Sursh Kumar and Socio-Economic Status Scale developed by Sunil Kumar Upadhyay and Alka Saxena has been used to collect the data.
5. **Statistical Techniques:** Mean, S.D. and two-way analysis of variance have been used for the statistical analysis.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table- 1(a) : Mean and S.D. of the Social Skills of Government and Non-Government Higher Secondary School students in relation to their Socio-Economic Status

Type of School	Level of Socio-Economic Status	No. of Students	Social Skills	
			Mean	S.D.
Government	Average	195	182.03	12.70
	High	93	213.27	12.31
	Low	12	154.42	15.44
	Total	300	190.61	20.50
Non-Government	Average	240	175.45	14.37
	High	43	207.74	10.11
	Low	17	144.76	7.04
	Total	300	178.34	19.42
Total	Average	435	178.40	14.02
	High	136	211.52	11.91
	Low	29	148.76	12.05
	Total	600	184.47	20.87

The table 1(a) shows that the mean scores of the social skills of students of government higher secondary schools who have average, high and low socio-economic status are 182.03, 213.27 and 154.42 respectively. These mean values indicate that students of government higher secondary schools who have average, high and low socio-economic status have low level of social skills. The mean scores of the social skills of students of non-government higher secondary schools who have average, high and low socio-economic status are 175.45, 207.74 and 144.76 respectively.

These mean values indicate that students of non-government higher secondary schools who have average, high and low socio-economic status have low level of social skills. It is also clear from the above table that the students of government and non-government higher secondary schools who have high socio-economic status have highest level of social skills.

Table- 1(b) : Analysis of Variance of the Social Skills of Government and Non-Government Higher Secondary School students in relation to their Socio-Economic Status

Source	df	SS	MS	F-Value	Results
School Type	1	6112.111	6112.111	35.483**	Significant
SES	2	136091.459	68045.730	395.03**	Significant
Interaction	2	98.516	49.258	0.286	Insignificant
Between Groups	6	20576650.3	3429441.732		
Within Groups	594	102318.609	172.254		

** = Significant at 0.01 level.

The table no 1(b) shows that at df 1 and 594, the first obtained F-value to compare the social skills of government and non-government school students is 35.483, which has been found significant at 0.01 level of significance. It shows a significant difference in the social skills of government and non-government school students.

At df 2 and 594, the second obtained F-value to compare the social skills of students in relation to socio-economic status is 395.03, which has also been found significant at 0.01 level of significance. It indicates that there is a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status.

At df 2 and 594, the third obtained F-value for the interaction of school type and socio-economic status is 0.286, which has not been found significant at 0.05 level of significance. It suggests that interaction of school type and socio-economic status has not caused a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students.

Thus, the sub-hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the social skills of government and non-government higher secondary school students in relation to their socio-economic status” is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Table- 2(a): Mean and S.D. of the Social Skills of Higher Secondary Boys and Girls in relation to their Socio-Economic Status

Gender	Level of Socio-Economic Status	No. of Students	Social Skills	
			Mean	S.D.
Boys	Average	209	177.51	14.22
	High	75	212.00	11.83
	Low	16	149.75	15.12
	Total	300	184.65	21.80
Girls	Average	226	179.21	13.80
	High	61	210.93	12.07
	Low	13	147.54	7.11
	Total	300	184.29	19.94
Total	Average	435	178.40	14.02
	High	136	211.52	11.91
	Low	29	148.76	12.05
	Total	600	184.47	20.87

The table 2(a) shows that the mean scores of the social skills of higher secondary school boys who have average, high and low socio-economic status are 177.51, 212.00 and 149.75 respectively. These mean values indicate that higher secondary school boys who have average, high and low socio-economic status have low level of social skills. The mean scores of the social skills of higher secondary school girls who have average, high and low socio-economic status are 179.21, 210.93 and 147.54 respectively. These mean values indicate that higher secondary school girls who have average, high and low socio-economic status have low level of social skills. It is also clear from the above table that higher secondary school boys and girls who have high socio-economic status have highest level of social skills.

Table- 2(b): Analysis of Variance of the Social Skills of Higher Secondary Boys and Girls in relation to their Socio-Economic Status

Source	df	SS	MS	F-Value	Results
Gender	1	118.281	118.281	0.650	Insignificant
SES	2	152660.763	76330.382	419.26**	Significant
Interaction	2	268.960	134.480	0.739	Insignificant
Between Groups	6	20570827.0	3428471.168		
Within Groups	594	108141.994	182.057		

** = Significant at 0.01 level.

The table no 2(b) shows that at df 1 and 594, the first obtained F-value to compare the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls is 0.650, which has not been found significant at 0.05 level of significance. It shows no significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls.

At df 2 and 594, the second obtained F-value to compare the social skills of students in relation to socio-economic status is 419.26, which has been found significant at 0.01 level of significance. It indicates that there is a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status.

At df 2 and 594, the third obtained F-value for the interaction of gender and socio-economic status is 0.739, which has not been found significant at 0.05 level of significance. It suggests that interaction of gender and socio-economic status has not caused a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students.

Thus, the sub-hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls in relation to their socio-economic status” is partly rejected and mostly accepted.

Table- 3(a): Mean and S.D. of the Social Skills of Higher Secondary Students of Rural and Urban Area in relation to their Socio-Economic Status

Area	Level of Socio-Economic Status	No. of Students	Social Skills	
			Mean	S.D.
Rural	Average	208	177.54	13.37
	High	73	213.38	14.10
	Low	19	148.05	6.86
	Total	300	184.40	22.27
Urban	Average	227	179.18	14.57
	High	63	209.37	8.32
	Low	10	150.10	18.84
	Total	300	184.55	19.41
Total	Average	435	178.40	14.02
	High	136	211.52	11.91
	Low	29	148.76	12.05
	Total	600	184.47	20.87

The table 3(a) shows that the mean scores of the social skills of higher secondary students of rural area who have average, high and low socio-economic status are 177.54, 213.38 and 148.05 respectively. These mean values indicate that higher secondary students of rural area who have average, high and low socio-economic status have low level of social skills. The mean scores of the social skills of higher secondary students of urban area who have average, high and low socio-economic status are 179.18, 209.37 and 150.10 respectively. These mean values indicate that higher secondary students of urban area who have average, high and low socio-economic status have low level of social skills. It is also clear from the above table that higher secondary students of rural and urban area who have high socio-economic status have highest level of social skills.

Table- 3(b): Analysis of Variance of the Social Skills of Higher Secondary Students of Rural and Urban Area in relation to their Socio-Economic Status

Source	df	SS	MS	F-Value	Results
Area	1	20.143	20.143	0.111	Insignificant
SES	2	152579.051	76289.526	420.89**	Significant
Interaction	2	842.819	421.410	2.325	Insignificant
Between Groups	6	20571302.7	3428550.455		
Within Groups	594	107666.273	181.256		

** = Significant at 0.01 level.

The table no 3(b) shows that at df 1 and 594, the first obtained F-value to compare the social skills of higher secondary students of rural and urban area is 0.111, which has not been found significant at 0.05 level of significance. It shows no significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary students of rural and urban area. At df 2 and 594, the second obtained F-value to compare the social skills of students in relation to socio-economic status is 420.89, which has been found significant at 0.01 level of significance. It indicates that there is a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status. At df 2 and 594, the third obtained F-value for the interaction of area and socio-economic status is 2.325, which has not been found significant at 0.05 level of significance. It suggests that interaction of area and socio-economic status has not caused a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary students. Thus, the sub-hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary students of rural and urban area in relation to their socio-economic status” is partly rejected and mostly accepted.

CONCLUSIONS

Following conclusions can be drawn from the present study:

1. A significant difference has been found in the social skills of government and non-government school students. Students of government higher secondary schools had better social skills as compared to the students of non-government higher secondary schools.
2. There has been found a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status. Students of higher secondary schools who have high socio-economic status had highest level of social skills.
3. Interaction of school type and socio-economic status has not caused a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students.
4. No significant difference has been found in the social skills of higher secondary school boys and girls.
5. A significant difference has been found in the social skills of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status. Students of higher secondary schools who have high socio-economic status had highest level of social skills.

6. Interaction of gender and socio-economic status has not caused a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary school students.
7. Significant difference has not been found in the social skills of higher secondary students of rural and urban area.
8. Significant difference has been found in the social skills of higher secondary school students in relation to socio-economic status. Students of higher secondary schools who have high socio-economic status had highest level of social skills.
9. Interaction of area and socio-economic status has not caused a significant difference in the social skills of higher secondary students.

Implications of the Study

On the basis of the findings of the study, it may be said that there is need to develop the social skills of the students. School management, teachers and parents can play a pivotal role in it. The school management should organize orientation courses, seminars and workshops for the teachers so that they can learn the new ways, techniques and tactics to develop the social skills of the students. Besides, workshops should be organized for students also so that they can interact with ne instructors in new situations and get acquainted with different social skills.

Teachers should motivate the students to participate in social gatherings, social activities and co-curriculum activities of the school. Teachers should adopt project method and community services to teach some specific topics. Teachers should try to inculcate the self-control and problem solving skills. Parents should teach and train their children in different behavioral skills since their childhood. Children should be inspired to discuss their problems, ideas and thoughts with the elders of the family and society. Parents should encourage their children to solve their problems themselves but they should always be available for their children whenever they need them. Parents should be in close contact of the teachers of their children to be familiar with the status of their progress.

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